

The role of social media in building strong institutions through citizens engagement in times of crisis

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Abstract

Citizens' engagement is one of the pillars of a democratic society. Through the years we have witnessed how citizens' participation evolved from small villages to the rest of the world through the power of information and communication technologies (ICTs). This paper aimed to examine the role of social media in building strong institutions through citizen engagement. Using the Social Media on the Citizen's Engagement Model, it analyzed the role of social media in building strong institutions. It also provided a platform for assessing how social media promotes good governance principles such as transparency, accountability, participation, and equality especially in times of crisis like pandemic. It is discovered that social media is a powerful tool that can help build strong institutions by facilitating a mechanism that promotes good governance principles through citizen engagement especially in times of crisis. Building strong institutions is possible if the government manages to mobilize and engage citizens and other stakeholders into action, social media in one way or another provides that platform.

Keywords: Social media, strong institutions, citizens' engagement, crisis.

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Introduction

Citizens' engagement is one of the pillars of a democratic society. Through the years we have witnessed how citizens' participation evolved from small villages to the rest of the world through the power of information and communication technologies (ICTs). We live in a media and communication-mediated world. Because of globalization, the world's situation is now more complex and complicated. The world is interactive, and the "truth" is always in question. Identities are fluid, new conjuncture brings the invention of traditions and identity markers slippery. The underlying imbalance between the economy, culture, and politics that we are only now beginning to theorize is what contributes to the complexity of the current world scenario (Appadurai, 2016). Globalization in the twenty-first century has greatly affected the sphere of common exchanges among individuals and groups. People from all over the world are interlinked together in different ways and means from physical to emotional and even social connectivity. As a result of the way work is organized, the flow of goods and services, and the exchange of ideas, people and places are becoming more connected (Perrons, 2004).

With this backdrop, this paper aimed to examine the role of social media in building strong institutions through citizen engagement. Did it serve as the fifth estate and help build strong institutions and an inclusive society? The Philippine Government's response to the COVID-19 pandemic was examined using the proposed "Social Media on Citizens' Engagement Model" to trace why social media as a platform is part of the discourse on strong institutions (Brillantes & Fernandez, 2008; Brillantes & Perante-Calina, 2018).

Synthesis of Related Literatures

Strong Institutions in UN's Sustainable Development Goals

A strong or effective institution is defined as an entity that levels the playing field and provides all citizens with opportunities to participate in and shape public policy (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012). Strong institutions were highlighted in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. The SDGs serve as a roadmap for achieving a better, more sustainable future for all. They deal with issues like poverty, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace, and justice, as well as other global problems we confront (United Nations, 2021).

In particular, SDG 16 is centered on peace, justice, and strong institutions (Monkelbaan, 2019). Specifically, this goal can be achieved if the society may create institutions that are efficient, responsible, and open at all levels (Target 16.6), guarantee public access to information, and uphold basic freedoms, by using both domestic and international agreements. In principle, strong institutions will result in an inclusive society that transcends racial, gender, class, generational, and geographic differences and assures inclusion, equality of opportunity, as well as the capacity of all members of the society to determine an agreed-upon set of social institutions that govern social interaction (UN DESA, 2009).

Social Media as the Fifth Estate

Social media have evolved into viable communication channels for both the public and private sectors (CivicPlus, n.d.; Fuchs, 2021). According to a Pew Research Center survey, social media is used by a wide range of demographic groups, occupies a sizable portion of their daily lives, and is beginning to replace time spent with traditional media. Additionally, local governments that formerly centered their public engagement efforts on conventional media are now focusing on social media (Elliott, 2018). Delaviz (2020) claimed that social media enables quick informative distribution, planned viral dissemination, and generally unmediated engagement between the government and stakeholders.

Meanwhile, Insignia Communications have identified reasons why social media is changing the way in which individuals discover about breaking news: (1) Usually surfaces on social media first; (2) Crosses geographic borders more quickly; (3) Is informed by a variety of first-hand, albeit frequently untrusted sources; and (4) Is debated by social media users who are engaged, which increases content sharing and distribution (CivicPlus, n.d.). Furthermore, in their study, about 77 percent of journalists use social media to research possible articles.

Social media as the fifth estate relies on its power as a public sphere that fosters discourse on diversity of thoughts and opinions on different matters, and as an echo chamber that maintains the status quo of perspective or viewpoints. It can be argued that the proliferation of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has transformed the public sphere. It allows a diversity of opinions between and among stakeholders. A study by Uwakala and Watkits (2018) revealed the potential of social media as the fifth estate that brings connection, interaction, and collective engagement among various groups of people. In their study the perceived inaction of mainstream media to an issue motivates people to participate in the protest (Occupy Nigeria) using social media.

Philippines and Social Media Statistics

There were 73.91 million internet users in the Philippines. There was a 4.2 million (+6.1%) increase in the number of users between 2020 and 2021. Internet penetration in the Philippines is at 67%. In terms of social media use, there were 89 million social media users. There was a 16 million (+22%) increase in the number of social media users between 2020 and 2021. It is found that 80.7% of the population used social media. In terms of mobile technology, there were 152.4 million mobile users. The number of mobile connections is 138.2% of the total population (Chua, 2018).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Social Media on Citizens' Engagement Model

The Social Media on Citizens' Engagement Model illustrates the double-edged sword potential of social media as a platform. The State (state actors) and citizens converge in social media to advance their respective interests. Citizen engagement is defined as means of communication between citizens and their governments. It may occur at any time during the design or implementation of governmental policy, the provision of public services, or be brought on by localized events (Participatory Methods, n.d.).

The model suggests that social media has the potential as a new public sphere in which discourses on various issues and concerns occur. Social media has also the potential as an echo-chamber for interest groups and filters information and messages for its members. Strong institutions provide a level playing field and give all citizens the chance to influence public policy and participate in its making. Institutions can harness the potentials of social media to promote good governance principles such as transparency, accountability, participation, and equity.

Methodology

This study used a qualitative method to realize the objectives of the paper. Literature was used as a basis to analyze the role of social media in building strong institutions anchored on the accounts and propositions of Social Media on the Citizen's Engagement Model. It also provided a platform for assessing how social media promotes good governance principles such as transparency, accountability, participation, and equality especially in times of crisis like pandemic.

Analysis and Discussion

Strong institutions bank on the aspects of good governance. It is governance that goes beyond the realm of the public sector. In other words, it is a governance that gives importance to the contribution of different stakeholders. Creating a space for dialogue and dissent is also necessary. The public sphere is important for societal communication because it is a socio-political space in which different thoughts and opinions are expressed, issues and concerns are discussed, and collective solutions are developed communicatively (Freudenthaler & Wessler, 2018). Holt (2004) suggests that the internet does increase the exposure of the public to political discussion and confrontation. Social media is used as organizing and mobilizing tools to foster change. The public relies on these platforms to shape discourse in the public sphere.

Filipinos have long realized the value of information and communication technologies (ICT) in their lives. They have been using these tools in diverse ways that enhanced their personal and professional relationships (Malindog-Uy, 2020). According to the House of IT, a tech company, social networking sites are one of the most engaging web-based activities in the Philippines. On various web-based social networking services, including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Snapchat, Filipinos are reported to be the most active users. These websites are now incredibly widely used that the country is called "Social Networking Capital of the World" (House of I.T, n.d.).

Alampay and Delos Santos (2015) studied the Philippine cities' use of social media. The study key findings are as follows: (1) The internet and social media have not been available in some cities; (2) City Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (CDRRMO) accounts

contain only a minor portion of the current city social media account; (3) When used for disaster risk management (DRM), cities’ accounts include a strong emphasis on readiness and preventative measures; (4) Social media account management procedures are casual and nonexistent; (5) Social media accounts for cities are strategically connected to pertinent regional and national accounts; and (6) Political changes might occasionally have an impact on social media accounts as well.

COVID-19 pandemic has also become a communication issue. There are a lot of instances that government agencies which are part of the Inter-Agency Task Force are not consistent with their communication efforts. There is an obvious misalignment on the part of agencies' communication people on its messaging strategy and mechanism thus, it creates confusion and unnecessary anxiety among the people. To prevent further misinformation and disinformation many Local Government Units see the opportunity to use social media platforms like Facebook to talk to their constituents and lay out measures that would prevent the spread of the virus.

We can take the Capital Town of Zambales, the Municipality of Iba, as an example. LGU IBA is the Official Facebook Page of the Municipal Government of Iba under the leadership of Mayor Rundstedt Ebdane. As of June 15, 2021, the Facebook Page has already reached 33,099 followers. LGU IBA is a platform for information dissemination of the Municipal Government of Iba and nearby communities. Based on the data gathered, content about COVID-19 and other related matters got the highest number of posts. While content about Disaster Management and Environment got the second-highest number of posts. LGU IBA Facebook Page was used as (1) platform to inform, educate and mobilize through the news and information about COVID-19 pandemic and government’s efforts and initiatives (Executive Orders and Ordinances), (2) platform of discourse through the learning sessions and stakeholder’s consultations on policy matters, and (3) platform for transparency and accountability through the updates on government’s subsidies distribution.

Table 1. Number of posts in LGU IBA Facebook Page

Themes	Number of Post	Percentage
COVID-19 and Other Related Matters	38	41
Disaster Management Environment	37	39
Business and Employment	10	10
Other Announcements	10	10
Total	95	100
Memo and Executive Orders	8	

Data Source: LGU IBA Facebook Page (Last Quarter of 2020)

The Role of Social Media in Building Strong Institutions

Strong institutions are effective, accountable, and transparent entities. Social media is a powerful tool that can help build strong institutions by facilitating a mechanism that promotes good governance principles through citizen engagement especially in times of crisis.

a. Transparency

Social media can be an enabling mechanism for transparency. In 2016, every political party and their respective candidates had their own social media account. Social media serves as a tool to communicate their platforms, programs, and projects. In 2020, the Local Government Unit’s Facebook Page will serve as a communication tool where important announcements such as

Executive Orders and Memorandum from the government are posted. Access to credible and reliable information promotes responsibility and accountability. In theory, transparency enables citizens to monitor and evaluate the government to account for its decisions and actions. What is crucial whether it is an election or response to the crisis, social media allow feedback mechanisms among the public. As per Governance and Social Development Resource Centre (GSDRC) Applied Knowledge Services, transparency can reduce opportunities for corruption.

b. Accountability

Social media allows the public to create, access, and process all sorts of information and misinformation. In that sense, every user of these platforms is accountable and responsible for their content. In 2016, the proliferation of fake accounts, misinformation, and disinformation hampered the opportunity to have a genuine conversation and to elevate the level of discourse among candidates and their supporters. The establishment of troll armies becomes an industry, paving the way for a shallow and divisive conversation among the public. In 2020, LGUs had decided to use social media to connect and interact with their constituents. An informed and politically active populace strengthens the demand for the government to be responsible and accountable (GSDRC Model). Social media gave way to online conversation among leaders and citizens. This mechanism that is present in the LGUs' social media accounts facilitates discussions, challenges citizens to think critically, thus encouraging leaders' responsiveness to citizens' demands that may lead to better access to goods and services. These LGUs' social media handles also serve as a platform to promote positivity despite the uncertainty. Stories of people helping each other can be found on those pages.

c. Participation

Social media allows active citizenship, one of the prerequisites of a healthy democracy. However, social media is also changing the way people think, feel, and do, changing who we are (The Social Dilemma, 2020). Although in 2016, political parties took the advantage of using social media to spread misinformation and disinformation, it allows the public to express their thoughts and emotions as well. Because of the COVID-19 pandemic that hampered mobility and face-to-face interaction, people have turned to their social media to engage themselves to connect and interact with their family and friends and participate in community affairs. Consultation and dialogue between the government and its citizens happen through online platforms such as Facebook Pages. This engagement can help citizens to understand and support government policies, programs, and projects and eventually develop a sense of ownership in the reform agenda. The government cannot do it alone, without public support, government initiatives are compromised which leads to its eventual failure.

d. Equity

Social media remains to be an issue on social equity. Not all people have access to these technologies. Adopting digital platforms such as social media is always in question due to many factors such as the readiness of the government to boost digital infrastructures in partnership with the private sector and the readiness of the citizens to adapt to digital citizenship. For example, they are required to secure thirty-five (35) documentary requirements and permits for every cell tower they plan to build (Gotinga, 2020). COVID-19 pandemic has forced government institutions to look into these problems because of the public demands for more and better internet service. Although the Bayanihan 2 Act suspends many documentary requirements for telephone companies

it will not permanently solve the red tape problems on the ground. The government needs to streamline the process for Telcos to meet the demand of the public. The Philippines can harness this opportunity as it transitions to e-governance and e-business.

Conclusion

Social media is a powerful tool that can make or break society. Social media is both a public sphere and an echo-chamber. Social media is a powerful tool that can help build strong institutions by facilitating a mechanism that promotes good governance principles through citizen engagement. It is a crucial and critical tool for citizens' engagement especially in the context of a pandemic world where physical and social mobility is challenged.

Social media can champion inclusivity and diversity. It is the fifth estate because of its capacity to bring people together and make collective decisions and actions. It is a platform for dialogue and dissent for the state and its citizens. It is a source of information and misinformation. Social media can foster good governance by building strong institutions by ensuring transparency of information, accountability of content-creators and users, genuine participation across sectors, and equity in access and control of technology. In the end, building strong institutions is possible if the government manages to mobilize and engage citizens and other stakeholders into action, social media in one way or another provides that platform.

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